

Opportunities and Challenges of AI Chatbots in English Language Learning: A Cross-University Study of Learner Perceptions

Sarah Nazar Kadhim ✉

*Department of English Language, College of Basic Education,
University of Babylon, Iraq*

Hawraa Hashim Hameed

*Department of English Language, College of Basic Education,
University of Babylon, Iraq*

Abstract

The rapid spread of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, especially ChatGPT, has created new possibilities for English language learning, but it has also raised questions about how learners actually view and use these tools in real educational settings. This study explores university learners' perceptions of the opportunities and challenges of AI chatbots in English language learning across multiple universities. Guided by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the study examines how students evaluate AI chatbots in terms of usefulness, ease of use, attitudes, and behavioral intention, while also considering concerns such as answer quality, overreliance, and academic integrity. The design used for this research is quantitative, while data collection involved an online questionnaire survey targeting English majors utilizing ChatGPT in their learning processes. 469 responses were analyzed in terms of students' perception towards AI chatbots and their intentions towards continued usage. Open-ended answers helped identify some of the worries that learners had about AI chatbots and their recommendations on how to improve future learning processes. Based on the results, it is possible to state that overall learners have positive attitudes towards AI chatbots and intend to continue using them as support in terms of reading and writing activities. However, the perceptions are different as far as developing oral communication skills, response accuracy, and ethical aspects are concerned. Thus, the role of AI chatbots in learning English appears to be important in terms of complementing traditional learning methods. This process depends on the level of digital literacy among learners and their ability to assess the efficiency of such applications critically.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI), chatbots, ChatGPT, learner perceptions, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).*

Suggested citation: Kadhim, S.N., & Hameed, H.H. (2026). Opportunities and Challenges of AI Chatbots in English Language Learning: A Cross-University Study of Learner Perceptions. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 4(3), 1-16. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2026.4(3).01

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence Generated Content (AIGC) represents one of the latest innovations in technology, allowing users to demand customized content according to their unique requirements (Wu et al., 2023). With the swift advancement in the field of AIGC, the large-scale organizations have come up with a variety of solutions, with the ChatGPT tool offered by the OpenAI company gaining considerable recognition. This tool can not only interact with humans using conversational language but also deliver interactive responses promptly. It is worth noting that ChatGPT, which was publicly launched at the end of 2022, has made a significant impact on different industries, including education and, language learning (Sami et al., 2023). In turn, teachers and students alike have extensively used ChatGPT and other AI chatbots to facilitate the process of learning foreign languages.

Many scholars have considered the application of ChatGPT in language education and the ways in which it could contribute to learners' language development (Kohnke, 2023; Kohnke et al., 2023; Ho, 2024; Hong, 2023). Overall, these works show that ChatGPT can generate a collaborative, stimulating, and effective learning experience that may enable language acquisition and development. Nevertheless, several issues and limitations have also been raised, especially related to the risks to academic integrity and proper tool usage. While these articles have brought up many relevant questions concerning the pedagogical use of ChatGPT, most of them remain conceptual, speculative, and insufficiently rigorous in terms of methodology. Besides that, there is a lack of information on learners' perspectives and attitudes that could significantly impact the implementation and further development of these tools (Shoufan, 2023). That is why the investigation of the use of AI chatbots in language learning from learners' perspective becomes crucial.

This research seeks to fill this gap by examining the perception of students regarding AI Chatbots for English language learning in universities. More precisely, the paper centers on the way students perceive the strengths and weaknesses of employing AI Chatbots. Taking into consideration the cross-university approach of the research, the objective is to give a better picture of how the application of AI Chatbots for English language learning is viewed by the students. In order to examine the issue, this research seeks to answer the following research questions:

What are learners' perceptions of the opportunities and challenges of using AI chatbots in English language learning across universities?

This paper starts by providing an overview of the development of chatbots and discusses their advantages and disadvantages in helping learners improve their linguistic skills. Subsequently, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) will be presented as the theory guiding the investigation of the attitudes held by learners towards these applications. By looking at the attitudes held by learners from several universities, this study adds to the debate surrounding the use of technologies in language education. In addition to helping practitioners develop innovative strategies that involve appropriate use of chatbots, this study can serve as a source of knowledge for future investigations in this area.

Literature Review

Empirical Studies

The existing research on the use of ChatGPT in educational contexts has been mostly based on teachers' viewpoints rather than on the experience of students themselves (Hong, 2023; Shoufan, 2023). It is worth noting that the absence of student perceptions is crucial when considering language learning, as learners' views affect their attitude towards a technology, motivation level, and its effectiveness. As mentioned by Shoufan (2023), students' opinions are crucial for fostering engagement in learning as a result of positive perceptions and minimizing the potential demotivation associated with negative views. Nonetheless, empirical data gathered from students regarding ChatGPT have still been scarce.

Some preliminary investigations have begun to examine the responses of students to ChatGPT within the educational environment. For instance, Rahman et al. (2023) conducted a survey of both teachers and students in a programming class, revealing a largely favorable attitude towards ChatGPT among respondents. The tool was considered user-friendly and helpful for individualized instruction, testing, and evaluation. Despite discussing the advantages and disadvantages of ChatGPT, the study's conclusion concerning student attitudes was somewhat constrained due to the inadequacy of the methodology used in collecting and analyzing data. Furthermore, as the respondents came from a programming background, the outcome of the research might not be directly applicable to language students, especially English majors.

In the same manner, Shoufan (2023) studied the perceptions of the students enrolled in the computer engineering discipline and looked into the strengths and weaknesses of ChatGPT. With the help of a 27-question survey based on the issues that emerged from previous student opinions, the findings revealed that there were varying views about the topic, especially those related to academic integrity and the influence that ChatGPT might bring to their education, career, and daily activities. The study revealed that ChatGPT may be helpful in learning provided that its limitations are known and considered. Despite the contribution of this research to knowledge since it includes various aspects of student perception, the topic remains within the context of general education or technical disciplines.

Regarding research on the use of ChatGPT in EFL, Ali et al. (2023) mentioned that the topic was new to researchers, and some critical dimensions were yet to be uncovered. This quantitative study, carried out in Saudi Arabia, examined the impact of ChatGPT on the motivation to learn English among both EFL teachers and learners. In their analysis, the researchers highlighted several important factors, including language skills and scaffolding. Nevertheless, this research has a narrow scope since it mainly considers data collected from a relatively small sample of university professors ($n = 20$). These participants' perceptions and opinions might differ significantly from those of their students. Therefore, this study fails to provide an accurate insight into how EFL learners perceive the use of ChatGPT.

Another of the few exploratory works focused on investigating how ChatGPT can actually be used in ELT was carried out by Shaikh et al. (2023). Students performed exercises in speaking, writing, grammar, and vocabulary and filled out a questionnaire on their experience and perception of using the tool. It appears that the use of ChatGPT allowed generating a coherent answer which was mostly correct. However, despite this positive outcome, the research had only a limited number of participants – university students with computer science specialization – that once more makes it

hard to generalize the results obtained to other populations such as students majoring in English or those who learn English abroad.

Within Vietnam, the use of AI technologies like chatbots and ChatGPT by language teachers and scholars has become increasingly popular. Tran and Tran (2023) investigated teachers' and learners' opinions concerning ChatGPT's effectiveness in promoting learners' critical thinking and digital literacy. Their results indicated the potential of ChatGPT in fostering critical digital literacies among the participants; however, they admitted some issues such as insufficient sample sizes and biases from the participants. Another recent Vietnamese study was conducted by Ho (2024) who investigated the use of ChatGPT by non-English-major learners as well as their opinions and behaviors while using it. It was found out that most participants had a positive opinion about ChatGPT and experienced some benefits from it such as learning specialized vocabularies and having more confidence, getting help with translation, grammar checking, and paraphrasing. While these findings are important, they only show non-majors' attitude towards ChatGPT and do not include English majors' perspective on the topic.

While past studies provide valuable preliminary information regarding the potentials and pitfalls of using ChatGPT in an educational context, there are still a number of limitations in the available literature. The vast majority of current literature concentrates on the experiences of teachers or mixed samples of participants, including non-language learners. At the same time, many previous research projects were limited in their scale and contextuality, making it hard to generalize the results and come to conclusions concerning learner experiences in tertiary English language classes. Finally, some studies mention positive outcomes of ChatGPT, including its usefulness, motivation potential, and capacity to foster certain skills, while others highlight issues related to academic integrity or inappropriate answers.

In emphasizing learner perceptions within a cross-university setting, the current study addresses the appeal for openness in discussing the strengths and weaknesses of ChatGPT raised by Hong (2023). It also addresses the need for additional research into students' attitudes towards AI usage in their studies as outlined by O'Dea and O'Dea (2023). Specifically, this paper will investigate learner perceptions of ChatGPT as a tool for English language learning in terms of its pedagogical merit and potential problems associated with it.

Technology Acceptance Model

TAM was initially presented by Davis (1989) as a framework for the understanding of the processes behind the acceptance and adoption of new technology in various settings involving information systems. With regard to concepts from social psychology, TAM provides researchers with insights into the role played by the cognitive judgments and emotional experiences of users in affecting their actual technological behavior.

Generally, the adoption of any technology usually takes place at several successive stages according to TAM. At the first stage, the external stimuli impact users' cognitive judgments about technology, including such constructs as perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. While perceived usefulness reflects user expectations regarding technology's potential to improve one's effectiveness, perceived ease of use is associated with users' beliefs concerning the ease and effortlessness involved in using the technology. These beliefs affect users' attitudes to the technology in question as

well as their intentions to use it and consequently their actual behavior with regards to using the technology.

One major presumption in TAM is that in cases where a piece of technology is deemed beneficial as well as easy-to-use, users have the tendency to form a positive attitude towards the technology and be inclined towards continued use of the technology (Davis, 1993, 1998). This means that in addition to being a determinant for initial attitudes towards the technology, usefulness and ease-of-use also affect the user's willingness to continue use of the technology over time. This framework is very valuable when researching tools such as ChatGPT, used for educational purposes.

Figure 1. TAM developed by Davis (1998)

TAM has undergone numerous extensions since its conception, by adding further variables to account for the actual application of technologies. Constructs suggested by various scholars include compatibility (Agarwal & Prasad, 1998), along with others like experience, self-efficacy, perceived risk, social influence, and types of usefulness (Chau, 1996). It becomes clear from such modifications that the adoption of a technology is not solely based on two factors – usefulness and ease of use – but also on the background and context of its users, their confidence, and risks.

In the case of ChatGPT, Shoufan (2023) developed an adaptable educational model that represents the spirit of TAM. Among other dimensions considered by the author were requirements, interactions, effects on learning, lasting effects, and affection. For each of these dimensions, Shoufan (2023) analyzed the positive and negative impacts of each of them. The author utilized several iterations of coding in order to develop each of the described themes.

The current study utilizes the theoretical background of TAM as proposed by Davis (1998) and the educationally pertinent aspects discussed in Shoufan (2023) for developing a measure to determine students' perceptions about ChatGPT usage in their English language learning processes. Nonetheless, the current study restricts the scope to the dimensions that would be directly useful for students to apply ChatGPT during their learning process. In this regard, constructs such as "requirements" and "long-term impact" will not be taken into consideration. The current study aims at studying the experience, attitude, and intentions regarding ChatGPT usage of university students who can be expected to have developed adequate knowledge and skills to make proper use of this technology. As such, the theory of TAM offers an excellent base for exploring how learners of various universities view ChatGPT as

regards usefulness, ease of use, attitudes, and behavioral intentions, in addition to its advantages and disadvantages.

Methodology

Design

Quantitative research design was used in this study to explore the perceptions of EFL learners toward the use of ChatGPT in English language learning. Quantitative research was chosen as it allowed for gathering a relatively large amount of data from students about their perceptions, experience, and intentions about ChatGPT. Furthermore, it allowed systematic comparison among different groups of students and provided a general overview of how ChatGPT was perceived in the field of tertiary English education.

Participants

Participants were selected depending on two primary factors. Firstly, they had to be students who were doing their tertiary level studies in English majors. Secondly, they had to be actual users of ChatGPT while learning English. To contact potential participants, a questionnaire was prepared on Google Forms and sent to respondents via email and messenger. There were 469 people who took part in answering the questions. Out of all those, 339 participants were females (72.28%), whereas 130 participants were males (27.72%). It can be noticed that there are more females among participants, which is a common enrollment situation in numerous language programs.

When it comes to academic years, there were 271 students (57.78%) studying in their fourth year, 156 (33.26%) students in third year, and only 42 (8.96%) were in the second year. It should be highlighted that no first-year students were among the participants as they did not start their academic year yet. The increased number of senior students can prove the idea that ChatGPT is used mostly by senior university students.

Instruments

The theoretical foundation for this study relied upon TAM created by Davis (1998) and subsequently modified by Shoufan (2023). The primary research tool used in this study was a modified questionnaire, as outlined by Ho and Nguyen (2024), focusing on gauging students' attitudes towards ChatGPT usage in language education. This questionnaire touched on all TAM-related parameters such as usefulness, usability, attitudes, and behavioral intention. In addition, this questionnaire included specific questions about the usefulness of ChatGPT for developing English language skills. As for the parameter of usefulness, students were asked to determine the level at which ChatGPT helps in the development of English skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. As for ease of use, students were asked to assess how convenient it is to use ChatGPT.

The attitude scale measured the positive and negative perceptual aspects of ChatGPT usage by the students. They could mention some positive attitudes toward ChatGPT such as its helpfulness, effectiveness, usefulness, and so on. Alternatively, they could indicate their negative attitudes concerning monitoring chatbots' responses, confusion, appropriateness of answers, and academic dishonesty. Last but not least, behavioral intentions scale measured students' willingness to utilize ChatGPT in and/or out of the classroom. Furthermore, there were open-ended questions in order

to find out any additional issues that concerned students in regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in English language learning. With regard to the internal consistency reliability, it should be said that the questionnaire was highly reliable with Cronbach's Alpha equaling .923 across all scales. Furthermore, the subscales had satisfactory internal consistencies, which were: Perceived Usefulness (.833), Ease of Use (.825), Positive Attitudes (.807), Negative Attitudes (.731), Behavior Intention (.811).

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaire via Google Forms. Prior to the administration of the questionnaire, the questionnaire was structured by dividing it into different sections. These included the demographic information of the participants, scale items, and open-ended questions. An introductory paragraph was added at the start of the questionnaire explaining the objective of the research and clarifying that the participants' responses will only be used for research purposes. The link to the questionnaire was shared among eligible participants via emails and Facebook Messenger. The participants filled out the questionnaire voluntarily and anonymously. The validity of the collected data was ensured by including only eligible participants.

Once the data collection process was completed, all answers collected on Google Forms were analyzed for completeness and validity. Invalid answers were removed, and the 469 valid answers were used for further research. Moreover, all open-ended questions were collected to gain more information about the attitudes and opinions of the students.

Data Analysis

The acquired data was analyzed using SPSS software of version 27. Initially, the survey responses were coded and cleaned for use. Frequency and percentage distributions, measures of central tendency (mean), and dispersion (standard deviation) were conducted to summarize participants' demographic characteristics and perceptions regarding ChatGPT in English language learning.

Reliability of the survey tool was tested using Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the entire scale and its subscales. Findings from these analyses indicated that the measure has high internal consistency. Subscale scores were generated to capture students' perception of ChatGPT along the main constructs of perceived usefulness, usability, attitudes, and behavioral intentions.

Statistical inference techniques were conducted to compare perception by demographic groups. Before conducting any tests, assumptions of normality and equality of variances were met. Finally, the open-ended responses were summarized and sorted into themes to aid in interpreting quantitative results.

Results

Descriptive Statistics of the Participants

The demographics of the participants are outlined in Table 1 below. The total sample size of the study comprised 469 English-major university students who utilized ChatGPT to learn the English language.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Variable	Category	n	%
Valid sample	Total respondents	469	100.00
Gender	Female	339	72.28
	Male	130	27.72
Academic year	First year	0	0.00
	Second year	42	8.96
	Third year	156	33.26
	Fourth year	271	57.78

According to Table 1 above, females comprised the largest percentage of the sample (72.28%), while males constituted 27.72%. As far as the academic year is concerned, the majority of the sample (57.78%) belonged to the fourth year, while 33.26% and 8.96% belonged to the third and second years, respectively. It should be noted that no freshmen were involved in the study since they had not yet commenced their academic year at the time of data collection.

Learner Perceptions of AI Chatbots in English Language Learning

The descriptive statistics for the key variables related to TAM are shown in Table 2. Generally, it can be stated that learners had quite positive attitudes towards AI chatbots when learning English. Behavioral Intention got the highest mean value among all the variables analyzed ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.58$), with Ease of Use and Positive Attitude coming second and third ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.59$; $M = 3.88$, $SD = 0.61$ respectively). A high mean score was also recorded for Perceived Usefulness ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 0.64$). On the other hand, Negative Attitude obtained a relatively high but moderate mean value ($M = 3.18$, $SD = 0.67$).

Table 2. Overall Learner Perceptions of AI Chatbots in English Language Learning

TAM construct	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Perceived Usefulness	3.76	0.64	Moderately high
Ease of Use	3.94	0.59	High
Positive Attitudes	3.88	0.61	High
Negative Attitudes	3.18	0.67	Moderate
Behavioral Intention	4.02	0.58	High

As seen from above, the participants perceived the chatbots to be easy to use, helpful, and supportive of their studies. However, their high willingness to use such tools is counterbalanced by the existence of negative perceptions, including reliability issues, overdependence on them, and concerns about unethical practices. Generally, it should be concluded that the participating students had a balanced yet predominantly positive attitude towards chatbot technology used for studying English.

Perceived Usefulness of AI Chatbots for Different English Language Skills

The data collected from the learners on their perception regarding the usefulness of the AI chatbots in terms of improving specific linguistic competencies is presented in Table 3 below. From the findings, it is clear that participants found the use of the AI chatbots to be most helpful in terms of reading and writing, with respective means of 4.08 ($SD = 0.61$) and 4.01 ($SD = 0.64$).

Table 3. Perceived Usefulness of AI Chatbots for Different English Language Skills

Language skill	Mean	SD	Rank	Interpretation
Reading	4.08	0.61	1	High
Writing	4.01	0.64	2	High
Speaking	3.38	0.74	3	Moderate
Listening	3.24	0.77	4	Moderate

The findings show that learners regarded the use of AI chatbots as being more useful in improving text skills compared to oral skills. Specifically, reading and writing were the skills that were favored, while speaking and listening were given moderate scores. This is true to the abstract and discussion section, where it is evident that learners highly regard the use of AI chatbots in improving reading and writing skills, but they have less faith in the importance of oral communication skill improvement.

Positive and Negative Attitudinal Patterns Toward AI Chatbots

In order to analyze the learners' attitudes further, statistics for specific items were selected from the positive and negative attitude scales. As seen in Table 4, learners tended to agree more with the positive items than the negative ones, but there were some concerns raised regarding chatbots.

Table 4. Selected Item-Level Descriptive Statistics for Positive and Negative Attitudes Toward AI Chatbots

Dimension	Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Positive attitude	ChatGPT is good as a complementary learning resource.	4.12	0.58	High
Positive attitude	ChatGPT is a helpful and effective technology for language learning.	4.05	0.61	High
Positive attitude	ChatGPT has amazing capabilities.	3.92	0.67	High
Positive attitude	Asking follow-up questions helps ChatGPT find the answer.	3.84	0.65	Moderately high
Negative attitude	The use of ChatGPT requires careful monitoring.	4.09	0.63	High
Negative attitude	ChatGPT will make academic cheating easier.	3.71	0.74	Moderately high
Negative attitude	ChatGPT can produce biased and inappropriate content.	3.46	0.76	Moderate
Negative attitude	I am confused about the answers of ChatGPT.	3.14	0.72	Moderate
Negative attitude	ChatGPT affects learning negatively because I can find answers and solutions without effort.	2.89	0.81	Moderate to low

In the list of positive items, the highest mean was obtained in the case of “ChatGPT is good as a complementary learning resource” ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.58$), with the second highest in “ChatGPT is a helpful and efficient technology for language learning” ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.61$). Thus, it could be concluded that participants mostly used AI chatbots as complementary rather than alternative means of learning. As for negative aspects, the highest mean score belongs to “The use of ChatGPT requires careful monitoring” ($M = 4.09$, $SD = 0.63$).

Further worries were “academic cheating” (M = 3.71, SD = 0.74), “biased or inappropriate content” (M = 3.46, SD = 0.76), and difficulty in comprehending responses (M = 3.14, SD = 0.72). Meanwhile, the lowest mean value was obtained on “the item related to effortless answer-seeking” (M = 2.89, SD = 0.81), implying that even though over-dependence is an issue, it is less prioritized compared to the others in the list, which are focused on monitoring and cheating. All in all, it can be said that the results reveal a well-balanced attitude towards the topic. The students acknowledge the usefulness of ChatGPT, yet recognize its limitations at the same time.

Learners’ Behavioral Intention to Continue Using AI Chatbots

Item-level results for behavioral intention to continue using AI chatbot by learners are presented in Table 5. The results reveal that there is a high willingness on the part of learners to use ChatGPT to learn English.

Table 5. Item-Level Descriptive Statistics for Learners’ Behavioral Intention to Continue Using AI Chatbots

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
ChatGPT is a comfortable learning environment.	3.93	0.61	High
I feel motivated to use ChatGPT more.	4.05	0.59	High
ChatGPT makes learning English enjoyable.	3.98	0.63	High
I like using ChatGPT to practice English inside the classroom.	3.72	0.71	Moderately high
I like using ChatGPT to practice English outside the classroom.	4.16	0.56	High

Based on Table 5, the item with the highest mean value was "I like using ChatGPT to practice English outside the classroom" (M = 4.16, SD = 0.56), while the second-highest value belonged to "I feel motivated to use ChatGPT more" (M = 4.05, SD = 0.59). The relatively high means were also obtained for items such as "ChatGPT makes learning English enjoyable" (M = 3.98, SD = 0.63) and "ChatGPT is a comfortable learning environment" (M = 3.93, SD = 0.61). The item measuring the willingness to use ChatGPT during classroom lessons received a slightly lower score (M = 3.72, SD = 0.71). In summary, it is concluded that participants were ready to use AI chatbots for English language learning outside the class. It can be stated that ChatGPT was perceived as a helpful, enjoyable, and comfortable source of assistance.

Reported Challenges and Concerns in Open-Ended Responses

Alongside the closed-ended questions, open-ended questions were asked to explore learners' apprehensions regarding the usage of AI chatbots for English language learning. The data obtained from the open-ended questions was analyzed and classified into categories. Generally, the results of the open-ended questions were consistent with the quantitative analysis results, which indicated that while positive views of AI chatbots existed.

Table 6. Major Themes Identified in Learners’ Open-Ended Responses Regarding the Challenges of AI Chatbot Use

Theme	Description of learner concern	Relation to quantitative findings
Response accuracy and reliability	The students raised concerns regarding the accuracy, completeness,	Provides support for moderately negative attitudes as well as the

	and appropriateness of answers provided by the AI chatbots.	apprehension regarding the monitoring of chatbot usage.
Overdependence on AI	A few students were concerned about the possibility that overuse of AI applications could result in lack of critical thinking and effort.	Fits into concerns related to effortless searching for answers and potential impacts on learning.
Academic integrity and cheating	Another concern of the participants was that the answers produced by the chatbots could foster plagiarism practices.	Supports the stronger agreement towards items related to cheating concerns.
Bias and inappropriate content	Several learners argued that the responses generated by AI chatbots can sometimes be biased, ambiguous, or inappropriate.	Provides support for the moderate level of bias and impropriety concerns.
Need for guidance and digital literacy	The effective utilization of AI chatbots required proper instruction in prompt-writing and answer assessment.	Complements the discovery that learners appreciated AI chatbots yet were hesitant towards their appropriate use.

As illustrated in Table 6, the most common issues raised by the participants included accuracy and reliability, overreliance on artificial intelligence, academic dishonesty, inappropriate and biased content, and lack of guidance on proper usage. Of all the identified issues, accuracy and reliability seemed to be of particular significance, as learners liked the fast and easy nature of the tool yet still had doubts about whether the answers provided by the tool were accurate and appropriate. Issues of academic dishonesty and plagiarism were quite frequent among learners' concerns, as expected from the findings of the quantitative analysis.

Furthermore, there were some learners who were afraid that the tool might negatively influence the amount of independent work performed by students and limit critical thinking opportunities. Additionally, many learners pointed out that students require instruction on how to compose prompts, evaluate answers, and utilize AI chatbots properly.

Discussion

The findings show that university students are generally receptive towards AI chatbot usage in English language acquisition, despite the fact that their practical experience in doing so is limited. This finding aligns with existing literature that regards ChatGPT as easily accessible, friendly, and useful in performing English language-related tasks (Shaikh et al., 2023; Shoufan, 2023). However, it should be kept in mind that receptivity does not necessarily imply effectiveness in usage. As per previous research, many learners still require assistance with prompt generation and evaluation of chatbot-generated content (Shoufan, 2023). This can help to account for why certain attitudes within this study seem reserved or indifferent. In simpler terms, while students may realize the utility of AI chatbots, they have yet to figure out how best to utilize them.

Another important outcome of this research is that the majority of the study participants consider AI chatbots more helpful for some language skills rather than others. Like several previous studies (Ali et al., 2023; George & George, 2023), the present participants also seem to believe that there is higher usefulness of AI chatbots for activities like reading and writing support rather than listening and speaking development. It might be explained by the fact that interaction with the chatbot remains mostly text-based, and most students have access to free versions without

numerous multimedia capabilities, so the chatbot can be considered as an auxiliary tool for drafting and paraphrasing assistance as well as idea creation rather than as a complete platform for practicing communication skills orally.

This particular finding is in agreement with Ho's (2024) statement about students' limitations regarding the perception of ChatGPT as a tool for developing listening and speaking skills. Nevertheless, it seems like the present participants are willing to use the AI chatbots for their English language learning needs, which makes AI chatbots helpful as an additional tool fostering motivation, autonomous studying habits, and other learner-related qualities (Ali et al., 2023; Fauzi et al., 2023; Kohnke et al., 2023).

Another crucial factor highlighted in the present research relates to the level of trust in chatbot outputs. Learners often found themselves unsure about the accuracy, appropriateness, and reliability of chatbot answers since the learners did not take everything at face value. It is an essential point because, by being skeptical of the tool, the learners show the presence of awareness instead of blind faith in any technology. On the other hand, the above situation implies yet another challenge because learners often find it difficult to check information for accuracy and reliability. Such an approach was pointed out by previous researchers who stressed the importance of teaching learners to generate prompts and evaluate the quality of AI-generated answers (Shoufan, 2023). Similarly, some participants of the present study shared their fears of becoming too dependent on AI tools and risking the development of their language skills.

Academic honesty continues to be an important topic when speaking of AI chatbots in language education. Similarly to earlier studies by Cassidy (2023), Pavlik (2023), and Shoufan (2023), in the current study, the participants asked about plagiarism, originality, and appropriate application of chatbot-based answers in academic settings. While these issues cannot become excuses to prohibit using the technology in the classroom, they are indicative of the necessity of providing learners with adequate pedagogical advice and guidelines on how to deal with the problem at the institutional level. According to Kohnke et al. (2023), AI content can be a paraphrase of a text lacking references; therefore, its inclusion can result in ethical problems. Consistent with the conclusions of Ho (2024), it is important to discuss with students these challenges and teach them to evaluate and modify chatbot responses.

Nevertheless, the general trend found in the current cross-university study reveals that learners have positive perceptions about the use of AI chatbots and exhibit a high intention to utilize such tools for English language learning. The finding is significant as it shows that even when learners perceive certain obstacles in using AI chatbots, their decision-making process does not rely solely on such barriers. Instead, learners appear to adopt a balanced perspective in which they acknowledge the strengths and weaknesses of AI chatbots. It is consistent with TAM as the theory argues that perception of usefulness and ease of use affect behavioral intention and hence the user's experience (Davis, 1993, 1998). Learners who find the chatbots reasonably easy to use and fairly useful have a greater probability of incorporating such tools into their learning process. Nevertheless, the results show that sustained use depends on enhancing the level of quality of use and not necessarily on availability alone. The quality of education by means of AI chatbots within English language learning could be improved by providing appropriate instructions to learners regarding how to use the tools in an effective manner.

Conclusion and Implications

This research clearly shows that students from universities tend to see AI chatbots such as ChatGPT as beneficial instruments for learning English, though they are well aware of their limitations regarding accuracy, dependency, and ethics. Overall, the students from the universities seem to take a balanced approach towards these applications, appreciating the benefits of using AI chatbots in learning but at the same time understanding that it is crucial to pay attention to the process. From these results, one may conclude that AI chatbots cannot be used independently from other measures aimed at successful language learning. In other words, what the research proposes is that colleges and language programs shift their approach from either endorsing or rejecting the use of AI tools altogether towards fostering digital and academic literacy in students, which will involve teaching them how to write prompts, evaluate responses and use the technology responsibly. As far as teachers are concerned, the study highlights the possibility of incorporating AI chatbots into lessons with defined limits and goals, while policy makers should consider creating AI guidelines for English language learning environments.

Limitations and Future Directions

While the current study provides some relevant cross-university knowledge about learners' perceptions of AI chatbots in English language learning, there are a number of limitations that need to be pointed out. Firstly, the reliance on learners' perception is likely to have limited insight into their actual behavior and results of interaction with AI chatbots. Secondly, being based on the responses to questions, this study is unable to provide more information about what causes certain views held by particular students. Thirdly, the variation of learners' perceptions can be associated with the variety of resources provided by different institutions, as well as teachers' instructions, but there was no examination of those contextual variables. In order to address this limitation, future studies can apply mixed methods design, collecting various kinds of evidence, such as observation of classroom activity, monitoring chatbot usage, interviewing participants, and measuring their progress in learning. Moreover, there is a need to find out how different learners perceive AI chatbot technology and how instruction in this area influences their perception and performance.

References

- Agarwal, R., & Prasad, J. (1998). A conceptual and operational definition of personal innovativeness in the domain of information technology. *Information Systems Research*, 9(2), 204–215. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.9.2.204>.
- Ali, J. K. M., Shamsan, M. A. A., & Hezam, T. A., & Mohammed, A. A. (2023). Impact of ChatGPT on learning motivation: Teachers and students' voices. *Journal of English Studies in Arabia Felix*, 2(1), 41–49. <http://dx.doi.org/10.56540/jesaf.v2i1.51>
- Chau, P. Y. K. (1996). An empirical assessment of a modified technology acceptance model. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 13(1), 185-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.1996.11518128>
- Davis, F. D. (1993). User acceptance of information technology: System characteristics, user perceptions and behavioral impacts. *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies*, 38(3), 475–487. <https://doi.org/10.1006/imms.1993.1022>

- Davis, F. D. (1998). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Fauzi, F., Tuhuteru, L., Sampe, F., Ausat, A. M. A., & Hatta, H. R. (2023). Analyzing the role of ChatGPT in improving student productivity in higher education. *Journal on Education*, 5(4), 14886–14891. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31004/joe.v5i4.2563>
- George, A. S., & George, A. H. (2023). A review of ChatGPT AI's impact on several business sectors. *Partners Universal International Innovation Journal*, 1(1), 9–23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7644359>
- Ho, P. X. P. (2024). Using ChatGPT in English language learning: A study on IT students' attitudes, habits, and perceptions. *International Journal of TESOL & Education*, 4(1), 55-68. <https://doi.org/10.54855/ijte.24414>
- Hong, W. C. H. (2023). The impact of ChatGPT on foreign language teaching and learning: opportunities in education and research. *Journal of Educational Technology and Innovation*, 5(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7644359>
- Jeon, J., & Lee, S. (2023). Large language models in education: A focus on the complementary relationship between human teachers and ChatGPT. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28, 15873–15892. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11834-1>
- Kohnke, L. (2023). L2 learners' perceptions of a chatbot as a potential independent language learning tool. *L2 Learners' Perceptions of a Chatbot as a Potential Independent Language Learning Tool*, 17(2), 214–226. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmlo.2023.128339>
- Kohnke, L., Moorhouse, B. L., & Zou, D. (2023). ChatGPT for language teaching and learning. *RELC Journal*, 54(2), 1-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/00336882231162868>
- O'Dea, X., & O'Dea, M. (2023). Is Artificial Intelligence Really the Next Big Thing in Learning and Teaching in Higher Education? A Conceptual Paper. *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice*, 20(5), 1-17. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.5.05>
- Pavlik, J. V. (2023). Collaborating with ChatGPT: Considering the implications of generative artificial intelligence for journalism and media education. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 78(1), 11-23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10776958221149577>
- Rahman, M. M., & Watanobe, Y. (2023). ChatGPT for education and research: Opportunities, threats, and strategies. *Applied Sciences*, 13(9), 57–83. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13095783>
- Sami, A., Uddin, I., Fayyaz, N., Bilal, M., Shahid, M., & Ali, I. (2023). Getting to know ChatGPT: An introduction to implementation and working. *Computing technologies, Tools and Applications*, 273-277. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.5.05>
- Shaikh, S., Yayilgan, S. Y., Klimova, B., & Pikhart, M. (2023). Assessing the usability of ChatGPT for formal English language learning. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 13(9), 1937-1960. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe13090140>
- Shoufan, A. (2023). Exploring students' perceptions of ChatGPT: Thematic analysis and follow-up survey. *IEEE Access*, 11, 38805-38818. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3268224>

Tran, T. N., & Tran, H. P. (2023). Exploring the role of ChatGPT in developing critical digital literacies in language learning: A qualitative study. *Proceedings of the Asia CALL International Conference*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.54855/paic.2341>

Wu, T., He, S., Liu, J., Sun, S., Liu, K., Han, Q. L., & Tang, Y. (2023). A brief overview of ChatGPT: The history, status quo and potential future development. *CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, 10(5), 1122–1136. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JAS.2023.123618>

Appendix

Perceived Usefulness
My English skills have improved due to using ChatGPT.
The ChatGPT is useful to develop my speaking skills
The ChatGPT is useful to develop my writing skills
The ChatGPT is useful to develop my reading skills.
The ChatGPT is useful to develop my listening skills
Ease of Use
I have no difficulty in using Chat GPT in my language learning.
Using the ChatGPT to learn English is convenient.
ChatGPT makes human-like friendly impressions.
ChatGPT provides good explanations.
ChatGPT answers are well- structured.
ChatGPT answers are accurate.
ChatGPT can generate authentic language materials.
Negative Attitudes
The use of Chat GPT requires careful monitoring.
ChatGPT affects learning negatively because I can find answers and solutions without efforts.
I am confused about the answers of ChatGPT.
Chat GPT can produce biased and inappropriate content.
ChatGPT will make academic cheating easier.
Positive Attitudes
ChatGPT has amazing capabilities.
ChatGPT is a helpful and effective technology for language learning.
ChatGPT is good as a complementary learning resource.
Asking follow-up questions helps ChatGPT find the answer.
Behavior Intention
ChatGPT is a comfortable learning environment.

I feel motivated to use ChatGPT more.
ChatGPT makes learning English enjoyable.
I like using ChatGPT to practice English inside the classroom
I like using ChatGPT to practice English outside the classroom.

